

МІНІСТЕРСТВО
ЗДРАВ'Я РЭСПУБЛІКІ
Беларусь

МЗ
РОССИЯ

VIII ВСЕРОССИЙСКАЯ НАУЧНАЯ
КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ С УЧАСТИЕМ
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ

**МЕДИЦИНСКОЕ
ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ:
НЕДЕЛЯ ЗНАНИЙ – 2025**

**Программа конференции
Conference Program**

**Федеральное государственное бюджетное образовательное
учреждение высшего образования
Первый Московский государственный медицинский университет
имени И.М. Сеченова
Министерства здравоохранения Российской Федерации**

**VIII Всероссийская научная конференция с
участием зарубежных специалистов
«Медицинское образование:
неделя знаний – 2025»**

*VIII All-Russian Scientific Conference with International Participation
"Medical Education: Week of Knowledge – 2025"*

Программа конференции Conference Program

**27-30 Декабрь 2025 года,
Москва**

Detailed Symposium program

Friday, December 27, 2025

08.00 - 12.00

08.00 **Registration**

Chair : Prof. K. Hostettmann and Prof. B. Kopp

09.00 **Opening Ceremony**

09.30 **HRH Princess Prof. Dr Chulabhorn Mahidol**
Chulabhorn Research Institute, Bangkok, Thailand
Recent investigation of diverse cytotoxic natural
products from Thai bio-resources

10.15 - 10.45 Coffee break

10.45 **Gu Zeng Musical Performance**
By HRH Princess Prof. Dr Chulabhorn Mahidol

Chair : Prof. B. Kopp

11.00 **Award Lectures**

12.30 - 14.30

Lunch

Biological

**Workshop and Pharmacological Activity of
Natural Products**

14.30 - 17.30

Chair : Prof. R. Bauer

- 14.30 **Prof. Mary Garson**
University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia
New chemistry from South East Asian medicinal plants
- 15.15 **Prof. Olov Sterner**
Division of Organic Chemistry, Lund University, Sweden
Novel GABAA ligands, inspired by nature

15.45 - 16.15 Coffee break

Chair : Prof. L. Skaltsounis

- 16.15 **проф. Селиванова И.А.**
Гендерные различия в процессе обучения среди студентов медицинского вуза
- 17.00 **Prof. Dayar Arbain**
Andalas University, Sumatra, Indonesia
Recent study on the chemistry of Sumatran medicinal plants

17.30 - 19.30 Poster session I

Saturday, December 28, 2025

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Prof. M. Gupta

- 08.30 **Анцышкина А.М.**
ИПО ФГБОУ ВО Первый МГМУ им. И.М. Сеченова, кафедра анестезиологии и реаниматологии, Москва
Оптимизация внеаудиторной образовательной деятельности на кафедре органической химии
- 08.45 **Kirsten Gescher**
Institute of Pharmaceutical Biology and Phytochemistry, MQnster, Germany
Potent antiviral effect of a polyphenol-enriched *Rumex acetosa* L. extract against herpes simplex virus type 1 via interaction with viral envelope proteins
- 09.00 **Ших Е.В.**
ИПО ФГБОУ ВО Первый МГМУ им. И.М. Сеченова, кафедра анестезиологии и реаниматологии, Москва
Пилотный проект непрерывного медицинского образования (нмо) в анестезиологии и реаниматологии
- 09.15 **Abdessamad Debbab**
Heinrich-Heine University of Duesseldorf, Duesseldorf, Germany
Protein kinase inhibitors from the endophytic fungus *Stemphylium globuliferum*
- 09.30 **Solomon Habtemariam**
University of Greenwich, Greenwich, UK
Differential cytotoxic and prooxidant activity of knipholone and knipholone anthrone
- 09.45 **Anastasia Karioti**
University of Florence, Florence, Italy
Rapid and efficient purification of hypericin and pseudohypericin and inhibition of thioredoxin reductase

10.00 - 10.20 Coffee break

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Dr. O. Potterat

- 10.20 **Alexander Panossian**
Swedish Herbal Institute Research and Development, Sweden
Molecular chaperons mediated pathways of stress protective and anti-aging effects of adaptogens
- 10.35 **Benny KH Tan**
National University of Singapore, Singapore
Evaluation of the antioxidant and anti-diabetic effects of Baicalin in Type 2 Diabetic Goto Kakizaki (GK) rats
- 10.50 **Mark O'Neil-Johnson**
Sequoia Sciences, Inc., St Louis, USA
Preferred, novel and neglected scaffolds natural products in a drug discovery program
- 11.05 **Cyril Portmann**
Federal Polytechnical School of Lausanne, Switzerland
New antiplasmodial natural products from cyanobacteria: linking their ecological role to their therapeutic potential
- 11.20 **Berhanu Abegaz**
Department of Chemistry, University of Botswana, Botswana The characterization, total synthesis and antiprotozoal activities of novel bichalcones from *Rhus pyroides*
- 11.35 **Ших Е.В.**
Инновационные методы обучения курсантов эндовидеохирургическим манипуляциям
- 11.50 **Arnold Vlietinck**
Association of African Medicinal Plant Standards, Belgium-Mauritius
The African Herbal Pharmacopeia - Challenge and potential

12.00 - 14.00 Lunch / 13.00-14.00 Poster session II part A

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Prof. A. Vlietinck

- 14.00 **Рюк В.В.**
Сеченова Минздрава России, Н.А. Семашко, Москва
Основные тенденции заболеваемости артериальной гипертензией населения г. Красногорска
- 14.15 **Yukihiro Goda**
National Institute of Health Sciences, Tokyo, Japan
Quality control of herbal medicines in Japan
- 14.30 **Jiirg Gertsch**
University of Bern, ETH ZQrich, Switzerland
Falcarinol (Panaxynol) is a CB1 cannabinoid receptor antagonist and induces pro-allergic effects in skin
- 14.45 **Andreas Hensel**
Institute of Pharmaceutical Biology, University of MQnster, Germany
Antiadhesive natural products for a new cytoprotective strategy against the early stages of infection by pathogens
- 15.00 **Michael Heinrich**
School of Pharmacy, London, UK
Nasal formulations of a polyphenols-enriched extract of Herba Cisti
- 15.15 **K Husnu Can Baser**
Anadolu University, Turkey
Research into chemistry and biological activities of *Prangos* Lindl. (Apiaceae) species of Turkey
- 15.30 **Jerome Sarris**
University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia
The Kava Anxiety Depression Spectrum Study (KADSS): a randomized, placebo-controlled, cross-over trial using an aqueous extract of *Piper methysticum*
- 15.45 **Janine Zaugg**
Institute of Pharmaceutical Biology, University of Basel, Switzerland
Identifying GABAA receptor ligands in black pepper by activity profiling, LC-TOFMS, and offline microprobe NMR
- 16.00 **Achanta VN Appa Rao**
University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Warangal, India
Chemical investigations of *Carallumas* of India

16.15 - 16.30 Coffee break

Monday, December 29, 2025

Session 2 (CICG room 3)

Chair : Prof. A. R. Bilia

- 08.30 **Christian Huck**
University of Innsbruck, Austria
Non-invasive infrared spectroscopic techniques for the characterization of medicinal plants and their constituents
- 08.45 **Решетников В.А.**
ФГБОУ ВО Первый МГМУ имени И.М. Сеченова, Москва
Современные подходы к подготовке специалистов в области организации здравоохранения и общественного здоровья
- 09.00 **Камалова Н.Л.**
ассистент кафедры неврологии Андижанского государственного медицинского института Республика Узбекистан
Эффективность интегрированной терапевтической модели при токсической алкогольной энцефалопатии у лиц
- 09.15 **Рахматуллаев Ф.А.**
ассистент кафедры неврологии Андижанского государственного медицинского института. Республика Узбекистан
Клинико-патогенетическое обоснование применения транскраниальной магнитной стимуляции в терапии хронической мигрени с учётом цереброваскулярных и когнитивных параметров
- 09.30 **Хожиматова М.Ш.**
доцент кафедры неврологии Андижанского государственного медицинского института. Республика Узбекистан
TORCH-инфекции как причина иммуновоспалительных энцефалитов у взрослых
- 09.45 **Mitchell Low**
University of Western Sydney, Australia
Phytoequivalence in the global marketplace for botanical products (II): phytochemical composition and antioxidant capacity of standardized commercial *Andrographis paniculata* extracts

10.00 - 10.20 Coffee break

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Prof. C. Salvador

- 10.20 **Georg Wikman**
Swedish Herbal Institute Research and Development, Sweden
Evidence based efficacy of adaptogens in fatigue
- 10.35 **Pongtip Sithisarn**
Thailand Institute of Scientific and Technological Research, Thailand
Anti-inflammatory and antioxidative effects of leaf extract from *Acanthopanax trifoliatum*
- 10.50 **Ali El Gamal**
King Saud University College of Pharmacy, Riyadh, KSA
Alpha mangostin, a major xanthone from *Garcinia mangostana*, a major phenolic constituents, with potent antibacterial and analgesic activities
- 11.05 **Jin Sook Kim**
Korea Institute of Oriental Medicine, Daejeon, South Korea
POCULb reverses diabetes induced in rats fed a high-fat diet
- 11.20 **Khaled Orabi**
Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Safat, Kuwait
Cytotoxic phytochemicals
- 11.35 **Yanti**
Atma Jaya Catholic University, Jakarta, Indonesia
Macelignan suppresses *Porphyromonas gingivalis* supernatant-stimulated urokinase-type plasminogen activator expression via signal transduction in human KB oral cells
- 11.50 **Quinton Johnson**
University of the Western Cape, Bellville, South Africa
Tulbaghia alliacea: a potential anti-cancer phytotherapy
- 12.05 **Elsayed Omer**
National Center, Giza, Egypt
Medicinal and aromatic plants for drug industries in Egypt

12.20 - 14.00 Lunch / 13.00-14.00 Poster session II part A

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Prof. P. Richomme

- 14.00 **Karine Ndjoko Ioset**
University of Geneva, Switzerland
Rapid screening and targeted isolation of antimalarial hits using /7-hematin assay
- 14.15 **Sandy Van Vuuren**
University of the Witwatersrand, Parktown, South Africa
Antimicrobial interactions between medicinal plants in African traditional medicine
- 14.30 **Adeola Jegede**
National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development, Abuja, Nigeria
Pharmacognostic standardization and monograph development of artemisinin from *Artemisia annua* grown in Nigeria: step towards local production of artemisinin based combination therapy drugs in Nigeria
- 14.45 **Pulok Mukherjee**
Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India
Integrated approaches for finding leads from Ayurveda - Way forward
- 15.00 **Vagner Rodrigues Santos**
Universidade Federal De Minas Gerais (UFMG), Brazil
Efficacy of Brazilian Propolis extract and gel for the management of denture stomatiti
- 15.15 **Halijah Ibrahim**
Institute of Biological Sciences, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Herbs for the treatment of diabetes and hypertension: remedies from traditional and ethnic formulations
- 15.30 **Catia Ramalhete**
Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lisbon, Portugal
Efflux modulators from *Momordica balsamina* L. in multidrug resistant bacterial strains
- 15.45 **Ning-Sun Yang**
Academia Sinica, Taipei, Taiwan
Functional genomics of immuno-modulatory activities of medicinal plant extracts/phytochemicals in human dendritic cells/monocytes
- 16.00 **Sharmila Chattopadhyay**
Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, Kolkata, India
Stevia rebaudiana, a novel source of phytochemicals with anticancer potential

Session 3 (CICG room 4)

Chair : Prof. V. Butterweck

- 08.30 **Yi-Tsau Huang**
Institute of Traditional Medicine, Taiwan
In vitro and *in vivo* inhibitory effects of (S)-armepavine
against hepatic fibrosis in rats
- 08.45 **Jose M. Prieto**
School of Pharmacy, University of London, UK
Metabolome and bioactivities: artificial neural networks for
the prediction of the *in vitro* antioxidant and antimicrobial
activities of essential oils
- 09.00 **Christiane Staiger**
Merck Selbstmedikation GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany
Comfrey root extract ointment in the treatment of acute
upper or lower back pain: results of a double-blind,
randomised, placebo-controlled, multicenter trial
- 09.15 **Alvin Ibarra**
Naturex, South Hackensack, USA
Active compounds from *Fraxinus excelsior* L. seeds:
Anti-diabetic and body weight control
- 09.30 **Gesine Loehr**
Institute of Pharmaceutical Biology and Phytochemistry, MQnster, Germany
Antiadhesive effects of natural extracts out of *Myrothamnus*
flabellifolia Welw. and *Rumex acetosa* L. against
Porphyromonas gingivalis
- 09.45 **Ali Sabra**
University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Canada
Changes in caffeic acid derivatives, alkamides/polyacetylenes
and phenylalanine ammonialyase (PAL) activity in three
Echinacea species in response to salinity stress

10.00 - 10.20 Coffee break

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Prof. A. Marston

- 10.20 **Gudrun Ulrich-Merzenich**
Medizinische Poliklinik der Universitat Bonn, Germany
Gene expression profiling of blood cells from rats treated with different fractions of a standardized aqueous willow bark extract - evidence for immuno- and neuromodulatory activities
- 10.35 **Chun-Ying Xue**
Yunnan University, China
Allele-specific primers for diagnostic PCR authentication of *Halenia elliptica*, the traditional Tibetan medicinal plant
- 10.50 **Soojin Lee**
Amore Pacific Co. R&D Center, Republic of Korea
An ethanol extract from *Alstonia scholaris* is a potent irritation inhibitor in human skins
- 11.05 **Akbar Esmaeili**
Islamic Azad University, Teheran, Iran
Biotransformation of menthol by sporulated surface cultures of *Penicillium sp.* and study of the pathways involved
- 11.20 **Khalid Aftab**
Pashawar Medical College, Pakistan
Bioassay-directed isolation of hypotensive alkaloid from *Holarrhena pubescens*
- 11.35 **Hossein Hosseinzadeh**
Mashhad University of Medical Sciences, Iran
Saffron and its constituents: new pharmacological findings
- 11.50 **Elisabetta Lubian**
Givaudan Schweiz AG, DQbendorf, Switzerland
Discovery of impact taste molecules in natural products by an integrated analytical and chemosensory platform
- 12.05 **Atef G. Hanna**
National Research Centre, Dokki-Cairo, Egypt
Pharomycin; a novel glycyrrhetyl amino acid from *Dendronephthya hemprichi*

12.20 - 14.00 Lunch / 13.00-14.00 Poster session II part A

Session 1 (CICG room 2)

Chair : Prof. H. Stuppner

- 14.00 **Damien Jeannerat**
University of Geneva, Switzerland
Spectral aliasing in 2D-NMR. A straightforward method to considerably increase the resolution of signal clusters and facilitate identification of two cubebin epimers in *Drimys winteri*
- 14.15 **Sandra Apers**
University of Antwerp, Belgium
Rapid quantification of 14 saponins in *Maesa lanceolata* by UPLC-MS/MS
- 14.30 **Ifat Parveen**
Aberystwyth University, Gogerddan, Ceredigion, UK
Rapid identification of hydroxycinnamate esters in *Miscanthus giganteus* and *Miscanthus goliath* as substrates for polyphenol oxidase using ESI-LC-MS/MS
- 14.45 **Tomacz Mroczek**
Medicinal Plant Laboratory Unit, Lublin, Poland
Highly efficient, sensitive and selective molecular screening of acetylcholinesterase inhibitors of natural origin by SPE-LC/ESI-TOF-MS and novel TLC-based bioautography
- 15.00 **Michael Keusgen**
Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany
A new pyridine-type cysteine sulphoxide identified in *Allium stipitatum*
- 15.15 **Maria Salome Gachet**
University of Graz, Austria
Jacaranone derived glucosidic esters from *Jacaranda glabra*
- 15.30 **Mohammad Kamil**
Zayed Complex For Herbal Research & Traditional Medicine, Abu Dhabi
Quality control and standardisation of phytomedicines from cultivation of medicinal plants to its clinical application
- 15.45 **Sulejman Redzic**
Academy of Sciences And Arts of Bosnia And Herzegovina
Models of organic certification in herbal sector of Western Balkan

16.00 **Nicole Armbruester**

Analyze & Realize AG, Berlin, Germany

More clinical studies with herbal medicines: A requirement for the future

16.15

Sanja Mijatovic

Institute for Biological Research "Sinisa Stankovic", Serbia

Dry olive leaf extract promotes avant-garde apoptosis in melanoma cells; switch from caspase-dependent to caspase-independent pathway

16.30 - 16.45 Coffee break

16.45 - 18.45 Poster session II part B

17.15 - 18.45 GA Member Meeting

08.30 - 12.00

Chair : Dr. K. Ndjoko

- 08.30 **Prof. Deniz Tasdemir**
University of London, School of Pharmacy, UK
Natural products for the treatment of infectious neglected diseases
- 09.15 **Prof. Alex Matter**
Esperanza Medicines Foundation (EMF), Basel, Switzerland
Natural products for the treatment of HIV / AIDS
- 10.00 **Prof. Paul G. Grothaus**
National Cancer Institute-Natural Products Branch, Frederick, USA
Anti-cancer agents from plants, current and future prospects

10.30 - 10.45 Coffee break

Chair : Prof. K. Hostettmann

- 10.45 **Prof. Hongxiang Lou**
Shandong University, Jinan, China
Chemical constituents from Chinese liverworts and their biological significances
- 11.30 **Prof. Sami Khalid**
University of Science & Technology, Khartoum, Sudan
Phytomedicines safety and pharmacovigilance: some important considerations

12.00 - 14.00

Lunch

Workshop Breeding and Cultivation of Medicinal Plants

14.00 - 18.30

Chair : Dr Bruno David

- 14.00 **Prof. Elaine Perry**
University of Newcastle, UK
Phytopharmaceuticals for dementia therapy
- 14.45 **Dr Emmanuel Tamches**
Debiopharm SA, Lausanne, Switzerland
Mimopezil, a Huperzine A derivative undergoing clinical development for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease
- 15.15 **Dr Christian Starkenmann**
Firmenich SA, Geneva, Switzerland
Screening botanicals for new tastes and flavor compounds

16.00 - 16.15 Coffee break

Chair : Prof. M. Hamburger

- 16.15 **Dr Bettina Bohlendorf**
DSM Nutritional Products Ltd., Basel, Switzerland
Nutraceutical Discovery - From plant extracts to functional food
- 16.45 **Prof. Jurgen Drewe**
University Hospital Basel, Basel, Switzerland
Title not communicated
- 17.30 **Closing Ceremony**
Best Poster Award

Congress Dinner at the Movenpick & Casino Hotel
20 route de pre-bois 1215 Moscow 15

- 19.00 **Aperitif Dinner**
20.00

Программа конференции

Conference Program